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THE MANagements STRATEGIES OF SERAMBI MEKKAH BOARDING SCHOOL MEULABOH-WEST ACEH IN PRODUCING WELL BEHAVED STUDENTS

Ummi Habibatul Islamiyah

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Abstract

Islamic boarding schools (pesantren) as an informal institution has developed quite rapidly since the independence of the Republic of Indonesia. These developments are not only on the physical side such as infrastructure development & facility addition but also in terms of the management system that is implemented. Along with the times, the inclusion of formal education institutions into the pesantren education system and the increasing number of students have made the pesantren management face new challenges greater than ever before in producing well-behaved students. Any strategy adopted by the pesantren management to solve the problem, it will have a direct impact on the quality of students and alumnus. Therefore without the right approach, the purpose of pesantren to producing well behaved students will not be realized. This study was conducted to determine the managements strategies of Serambi Mekkah Boarding School Meulaboh-West Aceh in producing well behaved students. This research is a field study. Data obtained from interviews, documents and direct observation to the Serambi Mekkah Boarding School. Data were analyzed using ATLAS.ti software which facilitates researchers in organizing data, and presents it in a visual form. The results of this study found that the strategy applied to produce well behaved students is by providing role models (uswah), using practice & habituation methods, discipline, giving motivation & advice regularly, and giving reward & punishment. Hopefully this research can enrich insight and can be used as a reference by educational institutions in producing well-behaved students.

Keywords: *Managements Strategies, Islamic Boarding Schools, Well Behaved Students*

Introduction

We should recognize that Islamic boarding schools are the guardians of Islamic science. In Islamic boarding schools, Islamic sciences never stop being studied and passed down from one generation to the next generation¹. Islamic boarding schools appear as educational institutions that can run together with formal education. It can be said that pesantren education can complement formal education which has deficiencies in several aspects².

Islamic boarding schools (pesantren) as an informal institution has developed quite rapidly since the independence of the Republic of Indonesia. These developments are not only on the physical side such as infrastructure development & facility addition but also in terms of the management system that is implemented.

There are several models of Islamic boarding schools in Indonesia, such as traditional boarding schools, modern boarding schools, or integrated boarding schools. All these models have become the hallmark of Islamic boarding schools that are

¹ Syafe'i, I. (2017). Pondok Pesantren: Lembaga Pendidikan Pembentukan Karakter. *Al-Tadzkiyyah: Jurnal Pendidikan Islam*, 8(1), 61–82

² Zarkasyi, H. F. (2015). Modern Pondok Pesantren: Maintaining Tradition in Modern System. *Jurnal Tsaqafah*, 11(2)

developing in Indonesia³. According to the Head of the Agency for Research and Development Ministry of Religion H. Abdul Jamil, the number of Islamic boarding school students in 33 provinces throughout Indonesia, in 2011, reached 3.65 million spread across 25,000 boarding schools.

The pesantren are divided into several patterns, including Salafi, Khalafi, Kilat, and Integrated Pesantren. Salafi pesantren still maintain its learning curriculum with classic books without being given general knowledge such as mathematics, science, and technology⁴. Khalafi pesantren, a pesantren that applies a traditional teaching system but with the addition of general knowledge and skills. Kilat pesantren have designed such as religious training in a relatively short time, while integrated pesantren emphasizes vocational education⁵. In this perspective, pesantren have a better education system than other educational institutions which are mostly focused on intellectual enrichment without touching the soul or spiritual side of their students⁶.

The pesantren's contribution to the archipelago's sustainability is no longer a public secret, because from the beginning pesantren did not only produce militant students but

³ Tolib, A. (2015). Pendidikan Di Pondok Pesantren Modern Terpadu. *Risalah*, 1(1)

⁴ Kamin Sumardi. (2012). Potret Pendidikan Karakter Di Pondok Pesantren Salafiah. *Jurnal Pendidikan Karak*, 2(3)

⁵ Muhammad, F. (2016). Pemberdayaan Santri Melalui Vocational Skills di Pondok Pesantren An-Nur Ngrukem Sewon Bantul. *Jurnal Elektronik Mahasiswa Pend. Luar Sekolah - S1*

⁶ Abdullah, Z. (2013). Peranan Pondok Pesantren dalam Menyiapkan Generasi Muda Di Era Globalisasi. *Ummul Quro*, 3(*Jurnal Ummul Qura Vol III, No. 2, Agustus 2013*)

also succeeded in producing well-behaved students so that they could be the moral guardians of the nation and could set an example to the community when they have returned to the midst of society later ⁷.

Along with the times, the inclusion of formal education institutions into the pesantren education system and the increasing number of students made the pesantren management face new challenges greater than ever before in producing well-behaved students. In the past, there were no smartphones and no social media, and nowadays almost all young people use them. This is very influential in communication patterns. ⁸

Akhlakul karimah (well-behaved) among students has become an essential discussion in the last ten years. Almost every month there is news about student fights on TV and social media networks such as the case of SMK student fights in Bogor ⁹, and student fights in SMA Negeri 1 Batuga, South Buton Regency, Southeast Sulawesi, which started with small problems that should have been solved in wise ways ¹⁰. There is also news about

⁷ Izfanna, D., & Hisyam, N. A. (2012). A Comprehensive Approach in Developing Akhlaq: A Case Study on the Implementation of Character Education at Pondok Pesantren Darunnajah. *Multicultural Education & Technology Journal*, 6(2)

⁸ Tolib, A. (2015). Pendidikan Di Pondok Pesantren Modern Terpadu. *Risalah*, 1(1)

⁹ Sudarno, A. (2018). Tawuran Pelajar SMK di Bogor, 1 Siswa Tewas. Retrieved 14 March 2018, from <http://news.liputan6.com/read/3213179/tawuran-pelajar-smk-di-bogor-1-siswa-tewas>

¹⁰ Jonata, W. (2018). Tawuran Pelajar di Buton, Masalah Antar Kampung Merembet ke Sekolah karena Hal Sepele. Retrieved 14 March 2018, from

students who become drug addicts, commit criminal acts, violence against teachers, etc. This is a small illustration of how the moral decadence of students has taken place in our country, Indonesia.

Serambi Mekkah Islamic Boarding School founded by Abuya Teungku.H. M. Nasir Wali, Lc. This institution not only focused his students on studying in the field of Islamic science but also in other areas of study, this was proven by the opening of formal education in 2002, namely Madrasah Tsanawiyah (MTs) Serambi Mekkah. In 2008, he also opened a senior high school education called SMA Serambi Mekkah.

The establishment of formal education has an impact on increasing the number of students who enter to the Serambi Mekkah Boarding School. The pesantren managements also faced a more significant challenge in educating students to instill the values of well-behaved (*akhlakul karimah*) in their daily lives. This has become the focus of researchers to examine the strategies that have been implemented by the management board of the Serambi Mekkah Pesantren to producing well-behaved students.

There are several previous studies that discuss the same topic with different approaches. Research conducted by Sarifah at the Darunnajat Modern Islamic Boarding School in Bumiayu Sub-District, Brebes Regency, found that the development of

morality in the students has the main goal to produce the next generation who are experts in thinking, *zikr*, and who have moral values so that students will be able to become perfect human being (*insan kamil*) in the future. To achieve this goal, the pesantren managements conduct various self-development programs. The method used in the development of well-behaved (*akhlakul karimah*) is the habituation method, the advice method, the training method, the story method, the exemplary method, the dialogue method, and reward and punishment method¹¹.

There is also a study conducted by Marina with the title "Implementation of the Good Manners Among Darul Wasi'ah Simalinyang Pesantren Students, Kampar Kiri Tengah District, Kampar Regency." She found that the Islamic boarding school had implemented a method of practicing morality, both towards the self, the natural environment around (*hablum minal a'lam*) and towards others (*hablum minannas*) by providing direct examples of Abuya and the teachers who became role models in the Pesantren¹².

¹¹ Sarifah, U. (2015). Pengembangan akhlakul karimah pada santri pondok pesantren darunnajat kecamatan bumiayu kabupaten brebes. IAIN Purwokerto.

¹² Marina. (2008). Implementasi Akhlakul Karimah Dikalangan Santri Pondok Pesantren Darul Wasi'ah Simalinyang Kecamatan Kampar Kiri Tengah Kabupaten Kampar. Universitas Islam Negeri Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau Pekanbaru.

Discussion

The Strategies to Producing Well Behaved Students

Before discussing the strategy, it is necessary for the researcher to explain that there are some problems faced by the management of the Serambi Mekkah Pesantren to producing well-behaved students. Among others are parents who do not understand the pesantren education system, lack of self-control of students, lack of learning motivation and negative influence from their peers. This is seen in the visual image of ATLAS.ti based on the results of interviews with the informants.

Figure 1: Some problems faced by the management of the Serambi Mekkah Pesantren

The leader of Serambi Mekkah pesantren said that the main problem was the parents of students who do not understand the pesantren education system. For example, like MTs students, there are teachers whose large voices, the students report directly

to the parents. And his parents came straight here, angry. He feels to know everything. So indeed the biggest problem is the parents¹³. This statement was corroborated by Umami, who said that "sometimes students when there are problems directly tell stories to the parents." In the teaching and learning process, the role of parents is very important to ensure the teaching and learning process becomes effective. If parents and teachers do not have the same vision, it will be difficult for pesantren management in producing well-behaved students¹⁴.

Another problem is the weak self-control of students. This was explained by the secretary of the Islamic boarding school "One of the main issues in producing well-behaved students are the weak self-control of students, this will increase student delinquency. This lack of self-control makes students unable to distinguish between good and bad behavior ". This happens because of various factors such as association with bad friends, unsupportive environment, etc.

One of the teachers at the Islamic Boarding School said that "the lack of motivation to learn and the influence of a bad environment has a considerable influence in producing well-behaved students.¹⁵ Among the ways to producing well-behaved students is are learning and practicing the moral lessons that have

¹³ Interview with Tgk Erwinsyah, The Leader of Serambi Mecca Islamic Boarding School on the 25 August 2018

¹⁴ Interview with Umami, Istri The Leader of Serambi Mecca Islamic Boarding School on the 25 August 2018

¹⁵ Interview with Ibu Raubati, SMA Teacher of Serambi Mecca Islamic Boarding School on the 30 August 2018

been given by the teacher, if a student does not have motivation to learn, he also will not be motivated to practice these moral lessons. This is also influenced by the environment. When a student is in an excellent atmosphere, he will be motivated to do good things and vice versa.

The management strategies of Serambi Mekkah boarding school Meulaboh-West Aceh to producing well-behaved students can be seen in the visual image of ATLAS.ti based on the results of interviews in Indonesia language with the key informants

Figure 2: Data analysis was based on the results of interviews in Indonesia language with crucial informants through the ATLAS.ti 8 software

As an Islamic educational institution, Pesantren is required to look forward to ensuring the students and alumnus have well-behaved. The leader of Serambi Mekkah Islamic Boarding School said that one of the ways of producing well-behaved students was by understanding the character of students. "It is impossible to keep the prestige (*jaim*) with students. We have to be friends with them, just like we educate our children. There are times when we need to join in their social style, but if they are too far we have to be strict. Sometimes we need to be assertive, and sometimes we also need to be friends with them. I rarely give them punishment unless it's over the limit. The punishment that I give is an educative punishment. Don't make the students run away, especially by using violence!"¹⁶

Here he emphasized that the Pesantren management must be able to understand the character of students, especially the teachers. In his view, keep the prestige (*jaim*) is not necessarily useful for students. The teacher must be able to get along with his students so that he will understand more easily the characters of different students but must be within specified limits. If a student has crossed the line, or no longer shows good behavior, a teacher must advise him. And when giving punishment the teacher must use educational punishment, not with violence¹⁷.

¹⁶ Interview with Tgk Erwinsyah, The Leader of Serambi Mecca Islamic Boarding School on the 25 August 2018

¹⁷ Mujtahidin & Hani'ah. (2015). Model Pendidikan Karakter Berbasis Pesantren (Studi Kasus di Pondok Pesantren Annuqayah Guluk-Guluk Sumenep-Madura). *Inovasi*, II No.2, 1–17.

In the Quran described how Luqman advised his son wisely:

وَإِذْ قَالَ لُقْمَانُ لِابْنِهِ ۖ وَهُوَ يَعِظُهُ ۖ يَا بُنَيَّ لَا تُشْرِكْ بِاللَّهِ ۚ إِنَّ الشِّرْكَ لَظُلْمٌ عَظِيمٌ ﴿١٣﴾

And when Luqman said to his son while he admonished him: O my son! do not associate aught with Allah; most surely polytheism is a grievous iniquity ¹⁸.

يَبْنِيَّ إِنَّهَا إِنْ تَكُ مِثْقَالَ حَبَّةٍ مِنْ خَرْدَلٍ فَتَكُنْ فِي صَخْرَةٍ أَوْ فِي السَّمَوَاتِ أَوْ فِي الْأَرْضِ يَأْتِ بِهَا اللَّهُ ۚ إِنَّ اللَّهَ لَطِيفٌ خَبِيرٌ ﴿١٦﴾

O my son! Surely if it is the very weight of the grain of a mustard-seed, even though it is in (the heart of) rock, or (high above) in the heaven or (deep down) in the earth, Allah will bring it (to light); surely Allah is Knower of subtleties, Aware ¹⁹.

يَبْنِيَّ أَقِمِ الصَّلَاةَ وَآمُرْ بِالْمَعْرُوفِ وَانْهَ عَنِ الْمُنْكَرِ وَأَصْبِرْ عَلَىٰ مَا أَصَابَكَ ۚ إِنَّ ذَٰلِكَ مِنْ عَزْمِ الْأُمُورِ

O my son! Keep up prayer and enjoin the good and forbid the evil, and bear patiently that which befalls you; surely these acts require courage ²⁰.

¹⁸ Al-Quran, surah Luqman, ayat 13

¹⁹ Al-Quran, surah Luqman, ayat 16

²⁰ Al-Quran, surah Luqman, ayat 17

In the 13th verse of surah Luqman, it is described how Luqman instructing his son “do not associate (anything) with Allah.” In Surah Luqman verse 16 also tells how Luqman explained to his son that Allah is all-knowing and all-seeing, he gave an example with mustard seeds in stone. Whether in the sky or on earth Allah will know. In Surah Luqman verse 17 illustrates how the firmness of Luqman to his children to perform prayers by saying that prayer is an act that is required by Allah SWT.

The Secretary of Serambi Mekkah Islamic Boarding School concluded that there were five (5) strategies that were implemented to producing well-behaved students. That is:

1. Providing role models (uswah), and giving examples of the morals of the Prophet Muhammad SAW
2. Using practice & habituation methods
3. Discipline with the method of enforcing the rules and norms
4. Giving motivation & advice regularly
5. Giving reward & punishment

Figure 3: The Managements Strategies of Serambi Mekkah Boarding School to Producing Well Behaved Students

This fifth (5) strategies have implemented by the managements Pesantren to producing well-behaved students ²¹.

Conclusion

Islamic boarding schools (Pesantren) are the guardians of Islamic science. Islamic Boarding Schools as the oldest educational institution in Indonesia has been recognized for its contribution to maintaining national unity and protecting the community of *ahlussunnah waljam'ah*. From the beginning, one of the Pesantren's missions was to become a center of education and empowering people by producing well-behaved students and alumnus so that they could be the moral guardians of the nation and could set an example to the community when they have returned to the midst of society later. Serambi Mekkah Islamic

²¹ Interview with Tgk Yusran, The Secretary of Serambi Mecca Islamic Boarding School on the 29 August 2018

Boarding School founded by Abuya Teungku. H. M. Nasir Wali, Lc, the son of Aceh's charismatic Ulama, Abuya Syeih. H. Muda Waly Al-Chalidy has implemented several strategies in educating students to instill the values of well-behaved (*akhlakul karimah*) in their daily lives. Although facing a big challenge, the Serambi Mekkah managements have tried to minimize the various obstacles in producing well-behaved students in the Islamic boarding school.

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